

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Agora: A Distributed Language Model Framework With API-Call Support for Integrated Climate Forecasting

ALEXANDRA UDRESCU¹ AND DAN-MATEI POPOVICI¹

Computer Science Department, National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest, 060042 Bucharest, Romania

Corresponding author: Dan-Matei Popovici (matei.popovici@upb.ro)

This work was supported in part by the European Union through the FUTURAL Project—Empowering the FUTure through innovative Smart Solutions for rURAL areas (HORIZON EUROPE) under Project 101083958, and in part by Unitatea Executivă pentru Finanțarea Învățământului Superior, a Cercetării, Dezvoltării Si Inovării (UEFISCDI) through the Project FUTURAL-Soluții inteligente inovatoare pentru zonele rurale (Orizont Europa Institutii) under Project 020234823. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

ABSTRACT We introduce **Agora**, a Generative AI-driven system that delivers expert answers and recommendations on climate and agriculture, transforming complex data into clear, natural language explanations. While built for the rural domain, **Agora** is highly adaptable and can be deployed across various domain applications. It operates as a “mixture-of-experts” language model system, selectively utilizing multiple fine-tuned large language models for inference. By dynamically integrating external data through API calls, **Agora** ensures real-time, contextually relevant responses. **Agora** is built for extensibility—it seamlessly integrates new APIs and domains without requiring a full system retrain. Developed entirely with open-source large language models from the LLaMA family, **Agora** remains open and adaptable, allowing anyone to extend and enhance its capabilities. Optimized for accessibility, **Agora** runs efficiently on commodity GPUs without compromising performance. By eliminating the need for expensive hardware like NVIDIA’s A100, it makes text generation more affordable and widely accessible. **Agora** outperforms closed-source models, achieving 78% accuracy on our question-answering benchmark. This result is achieved via dynamic API integration, which pulls in real-time external data, making responses more adaptive, precise, and context-aware.

INDEX TERMS API-call orchestration, API-call support, forecast generation, large language model, model fine-tuning, natural language processing.

I. INTRODUCTION

In many Eastern European countries, particularly Romania, a significant gap exists between the technological advancements and practices prevalent in rural areas. Despite the widespread availability of Internet connectivity Romania ranks within the top 54 of 140 countries for mobile Internet speed [1] and accessibility to expert data, smart services, and cutting-edge information remains low in these regions.

A report [2] from the Black Sea Basin Programme revealed that approximately **one million** people in Romania, along with their families, are **disconnected** from modern advancements. This is further supported by the statistics

The associate editor coordinating the review of this manuscript and approving it for publication was Arianna D’Ulizia¹.

shown in Figure 1. The same report highlights that 97% of Romanian farms are micro- and subsistence enterprises, typically family owned, covering up to 10 ha. These farms employ at least half the agricultural workforce available in Romania. Although specialized weather forecasts, seasonal cropping information, and insights into the effects of climate change are readily available [3], [4], [5], many potential beneficiaries in rural Romania are not utilizing them.

This disconnect arises because many rural users are unfamiliar with the technologies underpinning these services. The process of installing and navigating apps, datasets and API clients, coupled with the growing complexity of technical interfaces such as satellite and radar projections or multimodel forecasts can be daunting. Therefore, converting complex information into a clear, accurate, and specific

FIGURE 1. Awareness about smart farming applications [2].

text-based format is a key obstacle to the widespread adoption of modern smart farming practices in the near future.

As part of a broader effort to support rural communities [6], our objective was to develop a system capable of accessing expert data from diverse third-party sources, reasoning about such data, and delivering actionable conclusions and recommendations. By leveraging the power of Large Language Models (LLMs), which excel in processing, understanding, and generating human language, we aim to provide rural communities with easy access to expert knowledge and insights without requiring deep technical expertise.

LLMs, built on the groundbreaking Transformer architecture [7], have become state-of-the-art tools, attracting unprecedented attention and research effort, and are now widely adopted across diverse applications. They power chatbots capable of human-like conversations and improve programming tools with features such as code generation and explanation. The latest language models, with hundreds of billions of parameters, demonstrate advanced reasoning abilities and can perform logical reasoning to some extent.

However, language models are not out-of-the-box solutions for many applications including ours. LLMs suffer from **train-data dependency** - they are constrained by the data they have been trained on, thus limiting their reasoning abilities, as illustrated in [8]; **in-context reasoning limitations** - they struggle with fundamental reasoning tasks such as calculating minimum, maximum, or average values across data series, and often fail to decide when to perform factual checks instead of performing text generation; **prohibitive training costs** - they demand extensive memory and GPU resources, with fine-tuning costs starting at hundreds of dollars and escalating to hundreds of thousands for training from scratch.

In this paper, we introduce **Agora**, an advanced system powered by language models specifically designed to address queries related to weather forecasts, climate, and crop management, while effectively overcoming the challenges mentioned earlier. **Agora** can invoke third-party APIs to improve its answers. Moreover, it can efficiently **orchestrate** multiple API calls, allowing it to trigger additional requests when needed to retrieve supplementary data, thereby ensuring more comprehensive and accurate answers to user queries. For instance, to answer a question such as:

Can the cultivation of tomatoes thrive in the climatic conditions around the city of Pitești, Romania?

Agora recognized that simply retrieving data on optimal sowing conditions for tomatoes is insufficient. To deliver a precise response, it also initiates a secondary call to obtain historical climate data for Pitești. In another example:

What is the coolest month in the city of Sibiu?

Agora retrieves monthly temperature averages for the given location and sends them to an aggregation API to perform the **min** operation over the given interval.

In addition to answering questions accurately, **Agora** is highly **modular**. Instead of relying on a single large-scale model, it utilizes smaller domain-specific language models, each tailored to handle specific types of data. These models are coordinated by a larger **interviewer model**, that integrates and processes their outputs.

The domain-specific models that we trained focused on agriculture, weather, and climate data. However, **Agora** is flexible and can be deployed for a wide range of tasks, with the ability to scale and incorporate additional domains as needed.

Most importantly, by distributing expertise across multiple models, **Agora** is **scalable**. Using multiple models with a relatively low number of parameters, it supports training and inference that can be efficiently performed on commodity GPUs.

Agora addresses a key gap in current research, which is largely focused on training massive, general-purpose models with broad knowledge and billions of parameters. These large-scale systems—often proprietary—are out of reach for academia, small businesses, and other resource-constrained users. They come with usage costs and lock users into closed ecosystems. In contrast, we believe the future lies in smaller, high-expertise models tailored to specific domains. These models can be trained and deployed on modest hardware, are easier to evaluate, and rely on expert data to produce reliable, targeted responses. **Agora** is built with this vision in mind.

In Section II we outline the challenges encountered during the development of **Agora** and explain how its design effectively addresses each of these issues. We explain **Agora**'s implementation in Section III. In Section IV we discuss model training and evaluation. In Section V we provide an in-depth review of the existing approaches that follow similar directions. In Section VI we discuss limitations and finally, in Section VII we present conclusions and future work.

II. DESIGN CHALLENGES WHEN BUILDING AGORA

To begin designing **Agora**, we first explored the existing domain-specific models relevant to our areas of interest. The development of large language models (LLMs) has made significant progress in fields such as agriculture [9] and climate science [4], [10]. Such models were created by opting for a base language model, which may be either open-source

(e.g., the LLaMA [11] family) or proprietary (e.g., the GPT-4 family). Next, two main approaches are employed. The first relies on (i) **prompt engineering**, where the model is guided by instructions and/or examples to answer domain-specific questions, as seen in [4]. This may involve augmenting prompts with relevant dataset fragments and explanatory information to improve response accuracy. Alternatively, (ii) the model can be **fine-tuned** using a dataset of example queries and the corresponding target answers.

Our experience has shown that prompt engineering tends to perform well on large models (with more than 100 billion parameters). Fine-tuning can yield good results with much smaller models (e.g., the LLaMA2 7B model [11]). However, both methods are inherently constrained by their **reliance on data encountered during training**, which limit their reasoning abilities to that information.

Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) [12] is a common approach for addressing this limitation. RAG operates in two phases: first, a **retriever** analyzes the user query and retrieves relevant data from a database or external source. Second, these data are appended to the user query as context, which the LLM then uses to generate its response.

We found that typical retrieval components in RAG are often simple, typically employing basic search methods such as BM25 [13], which use keyword matching and do not scale well for complex numerical datasets. For example, considering the query from the previous section: “*What is the coolest month in the city of Sibiu?*”, a BM25-based retriever struggled to identify the specific dataset slice necessary to answer this query. At best, the entire dataset can be appended to a user query. However, this approach is impractical because language models have a limited context window (e.g., LLaMA 2’s 4096-token limit is equivalent to approximately 3000 words).

To address these issues, we examined methods that support invoking external APIs during text generation, such as [8]. The authors proposed a language model that has been trained to selectively pause text generation, invoke an API and incorporate the response into ongoing text generation. This methodology which includes dataset creation and the resulting model, is termed *Toolformer*. Toolformer leverages the inherent reasoning abilities of the small-size 6B-parameter GPT-J model [14] to automatically annotate an existing dataset with API calls. Subsequently, the dataset is used to fine-tune the same model to teach it where to perform API calls and how to select the appropriate parameters. Further details are presented in Section III.

By experimenting with Toolformer we identified five essential criteria that were essential in creating **Agora**:

- 1) **API-call support**: Our system needs to learn when and how to perform external API-involutions in order to support its answer-generation process;
- 2) **API-call orchestration**: In many cases, API responses may influence the construction of subsequent API-calls. For instance, for many user queries, we first gather data regarding monthly precipitation, then it, and

FIGURE 2. Agora architecture.

based on the resulting value search for crops whose optimal conditions match those precipitation averages. The system needs to support such dependencies between API-calls.

- 3) **API scalability**: New data sources exposed via new APIs should be easy to integrate without requiring an entire retraining of the system
- 4) **System scalability**: Training the entire system should be achievable on commodity GPUs, with minimal costs.
- 5) **Open-source reliance**: The system should exclusively utilize open-source models for inference, allowing for easy adaptation and implementation in various environments.

Of these five features, Toolformer satisfies only 1., 4. and 5. criteria. In addition, we found that criteria 2. and 3. conflict when attempting to create a single language model. As the type of orchestration between API-calls becomes more elaborate, smaller models tend to under-perform, and the data size required for training increases exponentially with the number of APIs. Therefore, in order to build **Agora**, we experimented with the idea of creating a multi-model system, that separates the tasks of properly addressing API-calls and responses, from the task of API-call orchestration.

III. AGORA ARCHITECTURE

The **Agora** was a central public space in ancient Greece where citizens gathered to discuss public matters and make decisions. Our system is inspired by Agora’s concept. It consists of a collection of models E_1, \dots, E_n henceforth called **experts** together with a special model MI , which we term the **interviewer model**.

Whenever a user query is received, MI , as well as all the experts generate one token at a time simultaneously on the same input prompt. At specific points during this process, when necessary, MI delegates control to an expert model E_i to continue the response. This process is illustrated in Figure 2, which shows the Interviewer model coordinating with three expert models. Each expert is trained to invoke API calls to retrieve data from third-party repositories, databases, or other external sources. For complex APIs, we train a dedicated

FIGURE 3. Agora architecture.

model to handle those interactions. In contrast, for simpler APIs that can be learned from examples, a single expert is trained to manage multiple call types.

Once an expert model E_i completes its task, control returns to MI , which resumes text generation until another expert is required or the response is complete. To clarify this text generation workflow, we provide an example in Figure 4. The user question is shown in gray. The text generated by MI is illustrated in blue, whereas that generated with the aid of expert E_1 is shown in orange. E_1 is the weather forecast and climate model. To properly address this question, MI notices that temperature information is necessary and uses E_1 to generate the appropriate text.

Figure 3 illustrates how the Interviewer model orchestrates API interactions between two expert models. In Step 1, the Interviewer delegates the initial part of the response to the first expert. This expert issues an API call and uses the retrieved data to generate its contribution (Step 2). In Step 4, the Interviewer invokes a second expert to continue the response. This second expert relies on the output of the first to construct a valid API call—highlighting a dependency between the two experts. Such dependencies can span multiple experts and occur in arbitrary sequences.

A concrete example of this interaction is shown in Figure 5, which involves two experts, E_1 and E_2 . E_1 specializes in climate-related data, while E_2 focuses on crop-related knowledge. As before, the question is shown in grey. Since climate data is needed first, the Interviewer starts text generation with E_1 . When crop-specific information becomes relevant, E_2 is engaged to continue the response. Finally, MI synthesizes the complete answer based on the outputs from both experts.

Next we discuss how each type of model (interviewer/experts) has been built.

A. EXPERT MODELS

Expert models are trained independently and their task is to perform accurate calls for a designated API (or APIs). In this work we consider four APIs: (i) **current date** - which is necessary when queries use time expressions

FIGURE 4. Generating answers with Agora.

relative to the current moment in time, such as *now*, *today*, *tomorrow*, (ii) **weather & climate** - which retrieves weather forecasts as well as queries related to precipitation, wind and temperature records for up to 10 years in the past, (iii) **crops** - which retrieves agricultural data regarding to optimal planting periods and precipitation requirements, from a collection of data-sources and (iv) **aggregation** - which computes maximal, minimal and average values over lists of integers. We trained three experts to handle these four APIs. Each expert model was trained via fine-tuning, starting from the same base LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct model [15].

LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct is already fine-tuned for instruction-following [15], making it a strong foundation for task-specific dialogue and assistant behavior. This means better alignment and usability out of the box—especially for structured, guided outputs like ours. Despite its smaller size, it matches or outperforms larger models such as LLaMA 2–13B and GPT-3.5, while remaining lightweight enough to run on a single commodity GPU [15]. Just as importantly, LLaMA-3 is open-source, giving us the flexibility to fine-tune and deploy the model privately, ensuring compliance with sensitive data requirements.

The API call representation is inspired from [8]. For a given API a , a call is a pair (f_a, i_1, \dots, i_n) where f_a designates the call name, while i_1, \dots, i_n designate the n parameters of the call. API calls are encoded as arbitrary word sequences identified only with special tokens marking the start and end of a call, as illustrated below:

$$\langle \text{API_CALL}_a \rangle f_a(i_1, \dots, i_n) \langle /\text{API_CALL}_a \rangle$$

Thus, during text generation, whenever the expert model predicts $\langle \text{API_CALL}_a \rangle$ as the next token to be generated, the following steps occur:

- The model continues generation internally until the complete sequence of the call, ending when $\langle /\text{API_CALL}_a \rangle$ is produced;
- The actual call $f_a(i_1, \dots, i_n)$ of API a is performed and the response sequence r is retrieved, and appended to the current context;

Through fine-tuning, expert models E_i learn how to construct valid API calls, and by carefully designing the training data, they also learn when API-calls should take place. In Section IV we go into more detail into our approach for training experts as well as dataset instrumentation. More details regarding the API syntax can be found in Appendix A.

FIGURE 5. Agora with two experts.

B. LIMITATIONS WHEN BUILDING ONE EXPERT ACROSS MULTIPLE APIS

Using careful instrumentation of the training dataset [8], a model can be trained to perform calls of multiple APIs. However, this approach does not scale well when the number n and the complexity of different supported APIs increases.

Suppose t_a ¹ is the number of fine-tuning examples that a model needs to train to accurately learn one API type (e.g. the *Weather* API). If a completely new and independent API type (say *Crops*) is to be added, another t_b examples would suffice. However, if we would like to capture possible dependencies between the *relative position* of one API call with respect to the other in the text (e.g. many *Crop* calls are likely to have a *Weather* call prior to them, and *Crop* answers may influence how the *Weather* calls are being performed), then the training data needs to have entries where one call occurs in relation to another (order $O(t_a \times t_b)$ entries), as well as entries where calls occur independently. Hence, the complete training dataset for learning the two APIs with dependencies between them is as follows:

$$O(t_a \cdot t_b + t_a + t_b) \tag{1}$$

This illustrates the **API-call scalability** problem highlighted in Section II. As the number n of APIs increases, the dataset size required to learn them increases *exponentially* with respect to n .

Moreover, the dependencies between API calls are not solely positional. Consider the example in Fig. 5. To assess whether peach trees are suitable for planting in the area of Constanta, we need to have knowledge about precipitation averages in Constanta from the *Weather* API. More generally, a response r from an API call may influence the manner in which another subsequent call is performed. Training data size is not the only limitation - as the number of fine-tuning

examples increases, small models such as LLaMA-3-8b are no longer capable of sustaining such intricate correlations, and their association performance degrades.

Thus, our solution replaces the “*single model*” scenario as well as the massive dataset required for fine-tuning, with several **smaller expert models**, each adapted to a given domain via a straightforward fine-tuning task. To correlate the text generated by such experts, we require another dedicated model.

C. THE INTERVIEWER MODEL

The interviewer model (*MI*) was trained specifically to handle the task of **expert model moderation**. More specifically, *MI* is responsible for deciding when an expert LLM should be used to generate parts of the answer, as well as to **integrate** these parts in the overall answer, whenever necessary. We implemented several options to achieve this moderation. The first, termed **sequential control**, is shown in Fig. 6. Informally, in this setup, “the interviewer *asks* an expert”. *MI* generates token sequences x_1, \dots, x_n . Next, it decided to use expert E_1 to continue the answer. This is achieved by generating a special token $CTRL_i$ ($CTRL_1$ in Fig. 6). Expert model E_1 uses x_1, \dots, x_n as the initial context (i.e. the sequence of previously-generated tokens). It generates tokens y_{n+2}, \dots, y_{n+m} , followed by a **STOP** token that returns the control to *MI*.

FIGURE 6. Sequential control passing between models.

When formulating a question related to plant cultivation *MI* might accurately decide to allow the *Crops* expert model

¹Our experience shows that $t_a \leq 10000$. More details in Section IV.

to continue generation. However, our initial experiments showed that *MI* does not always exhibit context sensitivity. Oftentimes, the expert is more capable of assessing the context and determining when to start "talking" by generating its own $CTRL_i$ token. Therefore, we also included another scenario, **parallel generation**, illustrated in Figure 7.

Here, the expert model *steps* and *interrupts* the *Interviewer*. To achieve this, we have all the expert models continuously generate tokens. As before, token y_k is generated by an expert based on the history of tokens x_1, \dots, x_{k-1} which represent the current context. When an expert generates a token $CTRL_i$, it preempts the *Interviewer*. All subsequent tokens up until *STOP* are part of the user's answer. In Figure 7, all tokens that the user does not see are indicated by dashed lines.

This situation often occurs when an expert decides to perform an API call. We observed that in almost all scenarios such a decision is contextually correct and should be prioritized over the text generated by the *Interviewer*.

FIGURE 7. Parallel generation with multiple models.

Finally, our experience has also shown that the expert-generated text needs to be **processed** before output. For this reason we introduced **Parallel generation with moderation** (see Figure 8). Here, we apply a text transformation function g to the sequence of tokens y_{n+2}, \dots, y_{n+m} generated by an expert.

FIGURE 8. Parallel generation with moderation.

If g is the identity function ($g(s) = s$), then the text generated by the expert is unmodified. If $g(\cdot) = \epsilon$ (the empty string), then the entire sequence generated by the expert is effectively hidden from the user. However, this sequence will still be part of the context which *MI* uses to generate text. In Figure 8, note that token x_{n+m+2} is generated based on the sequence of tokens $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n, y_{n+2}, \dots, y_{n+m}$, to which the expert *E1* contributed with y_{n+2}, \dots, y_{n+m} . This form of hiding tokens is particularly helpful in dealing with API-calls that produce tabular data as a response. For example, the *Weather* expert is trained to generate such API calls. We want this type of information to be in the context of the *Interviewer* to draw a conclusion, but not be explicit for the user. We illustrate this situation using the example shown in Fig. 9.

After starting a sentence, *MI* decides to yield the context to the *Current date* expert. The control tokens were omitted for brevity. The expert performs a call to retrieve the current date. This call takes no parameters. The actual call will be hidden from the user (illustrated with white boxes in Figure 9), but kept in the context window. After the expert has finished the call, control is resumed by *MI* which switches to the *Weather* expert. At this point, the current context contains the location as well as date, which will be used by the second expert model to construct its weather-related API-call. Once the call has finished, text generation control returns to *MI*, which uses the time and forecast information to produce its conclusion. This example highlights several key traits of our approach:

- We use API calls not only to generate text-answers, but also to add contextual information flexibly. By using g , we keep this information in the context so that the *Interviewer* can reason about it and at the same time hide it from the user. This is akin to dynamic generation of query-dependent *prompts*.
- The example in Figure 9 also illustrates the **dependency** between the answer given by the *Current date* API, and the construction of the subsequent *Weather* call. In practice we find many such dependencies, sometimes cascading over three or more calls. For instance, we might need to fetch the current date, based on it identify weather-related data, then perform an average over the result and finally fetch crop-related information based on that average.

IV. TRAINING AND EVALUATING AGORA

Agora was built as a result of an iterative refinement process, in which we explored different designs to achieve our goals. As mentioned in Section II, these were: (i) **API-call** support, (ii) the ability to support dependencies between calls i.e. **API-call orchestration**, (iii) the ability to easily integrate new APIs - **API scalability**, (iv) the ability to train the entire system on commodity GPUs (**system scalability**) and (v) **open-source** reliance.

A. FINE-TUNING A SINGLE MODEL FOR API-CALL SUPPORT

Our first step was to apply the Toolformer methodology [8], which consists of creating a single model fine-tuned to address our different types of API-calls. Toolformer selectively inserts API calls into a large dataset, enabling the model to learn when and how to generate them.

1) DATASET

Our methodology diverged from that in [8] because of the unavailability of such an existing dataset. Agricultural texts and datasets generally lack the sufficient temporal and spatial data required for accurate weather and climate API calls, with relevant examples occurring too infrequently for queries on optimal sowing conditions.

FIGURE 9. Illustrating the usage of the function g .

To build training data for each of our APIs—*Current Date*, *Weather & Climate*, *Crops*, and *Aggregation*—we used GPT-4o to generate separate datasets of question–answer pairs annotated with API calls. Ensuring diversity in these datasets was essential for the expert models to generalize effectively. We began by writing hand-crafted question templates that varied in complexity, involving between one and three experts, and capturing different types of dependencies across domains. GPT-4o was then used to produce semantic variations of these templates, using a range of prompts to encourage diverse language styles and phrasings. Finally, GPT-4o instantiated each template by filling in specific details—such as locations, crop types, or climate conditions—to create fully concrete questions. Using the selected parameters, we constructed a correct set of API calls, queried the relevant data and asked GPT-4o to generate an answer, together with the necessary API calls, resulting in a complete question–answer pair.

The prompts used for each API are provided in Appendix B-A, along with more details on the additional processing performed on the synthetically generated examples.

2) TRAINING

We chose a relatively small, state-of-the-art open-source LLM, specifically LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct, because the LLaMA-3 family consistently outperforms other models of similar size. We performed fine-tuning using LoRA [16] and QLoRA [17] adapters, to fit the memory GPU limitations. The exact hyper-parameters that we used are presented in Appendix B-C. To achieve objective (iv), we selected the NVIDIA AD102 GeForce RTX 4090 GPU, a

high-performance, cost-effective, and readily available piece of hardware on the market. We utilized three such GPUs each with 24,576 MB of available VRAM, accessed via the CUDA API.

3) EVALUATION

We began by identifying the main categories of user-relevant questions, with a focus on complex queries that require integrating information across multiple domains. This analysis included mapping out all possible dependency relationships between API calls. Our findings show that weather and climate data often serve as foundational inputs, with crop-related queries typically depending on both of these, as well as the current date. Aggregation API calls tend to rely on the results of prior API responses, such as those from weather, climate, or crop services. Based on these insights, we designed a comprehensive set of question templates that systematically reflect the full range of possible dependencies. Using an approach similar to that described in Section IV-A1, we generated diverse questions grounded in these templates. We then used GPT-4o—guided by the prompts described in the Appendix—to produce user queries evenly distributed across the identified categories, including examples involving only a single API call. These queries are distinct from those used in training (see Section IV-A1) and were not seen by the model during fine-tuning.

We subjected each of the systems under scrutiny to these questions and manually graded the answers on a scale of 1 to 5. Grades 3 - 5 are assigned to answers where all API calls are correct or only part of them, but the overall answer and underlying reasoning are valid. Grades 1 and 2 refer to

answers in which API calls are invalid and dependencies are misidentified.

For each query included in our evaluation, we have deterministic knowledge of both the specific API call(s) that need to be invoked and the dependencies between them. This predefined structure eliminates any ambiguity in the evaluation process, allowing us to assess each response with complete certainty and ensuring a rigorous and objective accuracy analysis.

The results are shown in Figure 10. *Accuracy* refers to the percentage of scored grades from three to five out of the total, while *Percentage of perfect answers* refers to those grades of five out of the total.

FIGURE 10. Agora performance compared to other approaches.

Our first experiments consist in applying the Toolformer [8] methodology on our training set, and with our language model choice. Although the results were promising (first row in Figure 10), and better results could be obtained by increasing the size of the dataset or that of the model, our observation was that the single model lacked the ability to associate multiple API calls, even though it had knowledge of each available API. Our attempts at instrumenting the dataset to capture API call dependencies revealed the API-call scalability problem discussed in Section III-B.

B. AGORA - INTERVIEWER WITH MULTIPLE EXPERTS

To enhance performance and add modularity (i.e. our objective (iii)), we introduced the **Agora** system, which distributes the API-call generation tasks across expert models, dependency handling and generating conclusions - to the *Interviewer* model. We used the same strategy as before to generate the datasets for the training of experts.

In our first **Agora** iteration, we used the same 8B base model for experts and the *Interviewer*. The training procedure for each expert model follows the details in Section IV-A2. Table 1 outlines the APIs managed by each expert.

For the interviewer model we used a system prompt that contained a short description of each API, a grammar showcasing their syntax and few-shot examples of their use. This system prompt, which can be found in the Appendix, enables the interviewer to understand how different APIs can

TABLE 1. The number of examples used to train each expert model.

Expert name	APIs handled
Weather & climate	Current date Weather forecasts Climate conditions
Crops	Sowing windows Annual req. precipitation
Aggregation	min, max, avg

be linked or combined when a user query lacks sufficient information for a single API call. Moreover, using a system prompt ensures the modularity of the **Agora** system because adding or removing one or more APIs requires only updating this prompt.

We observed a significant improvement in performance and **Agora** successfully chained multiple API calls, thus achieving objective (ii). The results are shown in Figure 10 (second column).

Our subsequent objective was to further increase the system performance. We experimented with a 70B interviewer model along with 8B expert models. This led to strong performance results, as shown in Figure 10 (third column), because the larger model’s enhanced reasoning abilities enabled it to better understand the available APIs and combine them. Simultaneously, new expert models can be trained independently, with no intervention required for the existing ones, and with minimal API descriptions that need to be added to the *Interviewer*’s system prompt, thus achieving objective (iii).

However, running inference on the 70B interviewer model with an NVIDIA AD102 is not feasible because of insufficient GPU memory, requiring us to switch to a more capable A100 with 80GB of memory.

1) MEMORY CONSTRAINTS DURING INFERENCE

Using LoRA [16] and QLoRA [17] adapters during fine-tuning, each expert can be formed by combining a base model with a small adapter, which can be easily plugged in or removed as needed (see Figure 11).

This strategy significantly enhances memory efficiency and reduced GPU memory requirements by up to three times, as reported in [16] compared with traditional fine-tuning methods. This approach offers several advantages for **Agora**’s architecture, which, in principle, is designed for $n + 1$ models, where n represents the number of experts together with the *Interviewer*. Because all $n + 1$ models must run for each generated token, we can achieve this by loading the $n + 1$ base models on a sufficiently large GPU (or multiple GPUs).

However, we can achieve better memory utilization by loading one base model on a GPU, together with k adapters, one for each expert. This means that on each GPU, we can run the inference from k different experts sequentially by simply

swapping out the corresponding LoRA adapters, as illustrated in Figure 11. This method reduces the number of base models that need to be loaded simultaneously, thus saving computational resources at the expense of increased time owing to sequential loading.

Additionally, when the interviewer model is significantly larger than the expert models, we can load the interviewer onto a dedicated GPU. The experts which are much smaller than the *Interviewer*, can be evenly distributed across the remaining GPUs.

FIGURE 11. Agora performance compared to other approaches.

Figure 11 showcases several scenarios used during our evaluation. In Scenario 1, four smaller GPUs run inference in parallel, an arrangement we used to assess the initial version of **Agora**. As the evaluation moved to the larger 70B *Interviewer* model, we transitioned to more powerful 80GB A100 GPUs. Scenarios 2 and 3 demonstrate how base models and adapters are distributed across available memory. In Scenario 3, for example, a single GPU holds one base model and two adapters, enabling inference for two expert models, E_2 and E_3 , which generate tokens sequentially. The adapter-switching time is approximately 20 times shorter than the time needed to generate a token. Despite hardware limitations, Scenarios 2 and 3 illustrate that our multi-model system can still operate efficiently, though with reduced performance due to sequential inference.

C. AGORA COMPRESSION

The primary limitation of the **Agora** system, as described in Section IV-B, is the substantial resource demands necessary to achieve optimal performance. This is mainly because of the need to load both the LLaMA-3-70B-Instruct model

(*Interviewer*) and the experts’ base model, LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct, resulting in excessive memory consumption. The memory overhead surpassed the capabilities of NVIDIA AD102 GPUs alone. To mitigate this, we developed a new, standalone model, which we trained using the responses provided by **Agora**. We call this model a “*compression model*”, because unlike **Agora**, it is a single language model, but is able to reproduce, and even enhance the performance of **Agora**. To achieve this, we proceeded as follows:

- We started with a dataset of questions and used **Agora** to generate answers. We employed an 70B interviewer and 8B expert models. This dataset includes examples demonstrating individual API usage as well as examples of chained API calls.
- **Agora** has great but not perfect accuracy, hence we carefully filtered it to retain only question-answer pairs with highly accurate multi-API call examples. The final dataset contains 17,000 such entries.
- We finetuned a single LLaMA-3-8B-Instruct model with this dataset, resulting our compression model.

The pipeline for training the **Agora** compression model, relying on the previous stages we have described, is illustrated in Figure 12.

FIGURE 12. All steps required to build the Agora compression LLM model.

While this model demonstrated the best performance overall, even slightly surpassing **Agora** with the 70B interviewer (Fig. 10), there were some trade-offs. The compression model:

- cannot be fine-tuned independently of **Agora**, as there is no existing dataset suitable for this task. Instead, the required dataset must be generated directly using **Agora**, or a similar tool.
- sacrifices modularity (i.e. objective (v)), meaning it cannot - by itself accommodate new APIs without resorting to **Agora** as previously described.

However, we found that fine-tuning the newer versions of a compression model is an acceptable compromise for various applications. The fine-tuning time - performed on an NVIDIA A100, is under two hours.

V. RELATED WORK

Our work lies at the intersection of multiple research directions in the field of large language models. Given the vast landscape, we organize the related work into three broad categories:

- **Specialized language models:** These are models trained or fine-tuned to address questions within a specific domain. In this category, we examine models such as ClimSight [4], KissanAI [], ClimaX [5], AgriBERT [3] and Agri1 [18]. Each of these has been developed with a clear purpose: to serve the unique demands of agriculture, climate, or weather-related tasks. They represent standalone efforts to embed domain expertise directly into the model itself.
- **Methodologies for Tool-Using Language Models:** These contributions focus on how we train language models to interact with tools — whether by invoking APIs, using external databases, or even generating tools themselves. The innovation here is two-fold: in the training methodology, and in the models these methods produce. Yet, to date, no such methodology has been applied to develop tool-using models for agriculture. As a result, direct performance comparisons with **Agora** or its compressed counterpart are not feasible, nor do they promise any insights. In reviewing these approaches, we focus on three critical questions that inform our own work: 1) *How cost-effective are these methods?* 2) *Do they support chaining of API calls?* 3) *Can they generalize to arbitrary APIs?*
- **Multi-model systems and Knowledge distillation:** These works share architectural similarities with our own work. Some construct systems composed of multiple language models, echoing the design of **Agora**. Others focus on transferring knowledge from larger models to smaller ones — a strategy central to our compression model.

A. SPECIALIZED LANGUAGE MODELS

Since the release of OpenAI’s models, interest in developing domain-specific language models has surged — including in fields like weather, climate, and agriculture. And yet, none of the existing models mirror the structure or intent of our own. Each is narrowly focused, tailored to a distinct subset of problems or datasets. As we discussed in Section II, these models remain fundamentally limited by the scope of their training: they can only reason within the bounds of the data and expertise they were exposed to.

Since the advent of OpenAI’s models there is a growing interest in developing **domain-specific models** including those for areas such as weather, climate, and agriculture. Our research suggests that no such existing model shares similarities or expertise to our own, each being focused on particular areas. Also, as mentioned in Section II, all such models are limited to the scope of expertise and data they have seen during training.

ClimSight [4] is a prototype designed to answer location-specific climate questions by combining geographic and climate data into a prompt fed to GPT-4. While it effectively translates expert data for public use, it remains constrained by its reliance on a proprietary model, limiting accessibility and flexibility. Its prompt-based structure also restricts the range of questions it can handle, especially those involving complex comparisons or evolving climate scenarios.

KissanAI [9] is a startup focused on supporting farmers through a multilingual chatbot that offers guidance for informed agricultural decision-making. Built on top of OpenAI’s language models, its architecture follows a familiar pattern seen in other similar systems. However, like all tools that rely on GPT-based models, KissanAI is inherently limited — it cannot access or integrate dynamic third-party data, and its performance is ultimately bound by the capabilities of the underlying proprietary model. KissanAI is unable to integrate real-time weather data nor is it capable of being seamlessly extended to use external databases.

ClimaX [5] is a state-of-the-art language model built from the ground up for climate forecasting. Unlike general-purpose models trained on arbitrary text, ClimaX was trained on structured weather variables, using a custom tokenization strategy tailored specifically for this task. Its foundation is CMIP6 — a comprehensive dataset of climate simulations encompassing over 100 climate models and 49 distinct climate scenarios. This makes ClimaX fundamentally different from models like KissanAI or ClimSight in two important ways:

- it is not fine-tuned from a general model, but rather pre-trained from scratch using a transformer architecture and later fine-tuned for forecasting;
- it is not a general-purpose chatbot or assistant, but a domain-specific model with a singular focus — predicting the climate.

However, ClimaX operates in isolation. It does not support external data retrieval or dynamic inputs via APIs. It belongs to a broader class of machine learning models focused on forecasting and data modeling, as reviewed in [19]. Our work, by contrast, avoids direct modeling in favor of integrating outputs from multiple forecasting sources — aiming to create a cohesive system that reasons across models, rather than replacing them.

AgriBERT [3] is a compact language model trained from the ground up, combining the original dataset used for BERT [20] with a large corpus of agricultural literature. The key contribution of [3] lies in this integration — blending general linguistic knowledge with domain-specific expertise in agriculture and nutrition.

Although developed independently of BERT, AgriBERT retains the architectural advantages of its predecessor while outperforming similar models on fundamental tasks, such as selecting the correct answer from a list in agriculture-related question sets. It demonstrates the potential of smaller, decoder-only models when focused on narrow, well-defined domains. As previous examples, AgriBERT only focuses on

TABLE 2. A review of existing agriculture and climate models.

Name	Base model	Model adaptation	API support	Expertise
ClimSight [4]	GPT 4	prompt engineering	no	climate
KissanAI [9]	OpenAI models	undisclosed	no	agriculture
ClimaX [5]	-	training & fine-tuning	no	climate
AgriBERT [3]	BERT	training & fine-tuning	no	agriculture
Agri1 [9]	OpenAI models	undisclosed	no	agriculture

agricultural data, without including information related to weather or climate change, and without means to use external data.

Agri1 [18] is a proprietary, closed-source system built on top of OpenAI’s language models, following a design approach similar to that of KissanAI. Positioned as a commercial product, Agri1 offers support for agriculture-related inquiries, including pest control, plant disease identification, soil analysis, and crop fertilization strategies. Despite its practical scope, little is publicly known about Agri1’s development or performance benchmarks. What is clear, however, is that Agri1, like other systems based on proprietary models, lacks the ability to integrate external or dynamic data — a limitation that restricts its adaptability and long-term scalability.

Table 2 provides a summary of all the models we have examined. Most rely on OpenAI’s proprietary technologies, which inherently limits their accessibility — usage comes at a cost, and extensibility is constrained. Moreover, none of these models support integration with external data sources. Not even through Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), a powerful approach that blends search and generation to incorporate real-time, factual information. For a broader overview of RAG-based methods, we refer the interested reader to the survey in [21]. In the end, no existing model spans the range of expertise our work requires. Each falls short when it comes to crossing domain boundaries or adapting to diverse, dynamic contexts.

B. METHODOLOGIES FOR TOOL-USING LANGUAGE MODELS

In this section, we explore a broad landscape of methods developed to enable language models to interact with third-party tools, call external APIs, and, in some cases, even generate new tools for future use. The body of work is extensive — rich in overlapping ideas and functionality, yet often diverging in key design choices and assumptions. To frame our analysis, we focus on four critical dimensions:

- 1) *Cost-effectiveness*: What are the resource and time requirements for training and what model sizes are used? In our view, models exceeding 70 billion parameters are prohibitively resource-intensive and impractical for scalable use in our setting.
- 2) *API-call chaining*: Do these models support chaining API calls, allowing for more complex reasoning as discussed earlier?

- 3) *Integration of new APIs*: How adaptable are these methods when introducing unseen APIs? Can they be retrained efficiently to incorporate new tools or data sources?
- 4) *Support for data retrieval*: Many APIs serve as tools for various tasks, most common being computation and image processing. However, their suitability for data retrieval and interpretation—central to our task—is not straightforward.

We begin with Toolformer [8], the foundational work that shaped the early direction of our research. Its methodology served as a starting point, and we explore its limitations in greater detail in Sections III-A and III-C. Among all existing approaches, Toolformer is the only one we actively replicated and directly compared to our own. It provided the groundwork for the iterative improvements that followed — a baseline from which our methodology evolved.

Craft [22] is an LLM-based system focused on generating new, task-specific tools — executable code snippets — rather than relying on existing ones to improve language model performance. These tools are particularly useful for advanced mathematical reasoning, where standard text generation often falls short.

Craft follows a four-step pipeline:

- It begins by curating a large dataset of input-output pairs tailored to each task.
- GPT-4 is then used to generate Python code solutions for these problems.
- These solutions are merged into more general, reusable functions.
- A validation phase ensures correctness, followed by a de-duplication step to eliminate redundancy.

While Craft demonstrates strong capabilities in complex reasoning — far beyond simple operations like min, max, or average — it is **not designed for integrating or reasoning over external data**. Moreover, Craft relies proprietary models, thus hindering its deployment for other tasks. As such, it is not directly applicable to our use case, though it remains an impressive example of code-driven reasoning powered by language models.

ToolLLM [23] is a framework designed to replicate ChatGPT’s ability to interact with external tools and APIs—within an open-source ecosystem. Its methodology closely parallels the compression model approach discussed in Section IV-C. The authors constructed a synthetic instruction-tuning dataset using ChatGPT, covering over 16,000 real-world RESTful APIs sourced from RapidAPI. ChatGPT was used both

TABLE 3. A review of existing agriculture and climate models.

Name	Base model	integration of new APIs	API-call chaining	Support for data retrieval
Toolformer [8]	GPT-J (6B)	✗	✗	✗
Craft [22]	GPT 3.5 turbo	n/a	n/a	✗
ToolLLM [23]	LLaMA-2 (7B)	✗	✗	✓
Confucius [24]	LLaMA-2 (7B)	✓	✗	✓
Gorilla [25]	LLaMA-2 (7B)	✓	✗	✗
GPT4Tools [26]	Vicuna-13B [27]	✗	✗	✗
ToolAlpaca [28]	ChatGPT	✓	✗	✓
CREATOR [29]	Vicuna-7B (7B) & Vicuna-13B [27]	✗	✗	✗
LATM [30]	GPT-3.5 & GPT-4	✗	✗	✗
ToolkenGPT [31]	LLaMA-2 (13B)	✓	✗	✗
Agora	LLaMA-3 8B	✓	✓	✓

to simulate usage scenarios and to generate corresponding solutions. This dataset was then used to train ToolLLaMA, an open-source model paired with an API retriever. The results are notable: ToolLLaMA, a 7B-parameter model deployable on standard hardware, achieves performance comparable to ChatGPT in many API-related tasks. These findings align with our own, confirming that task-specific capabilities of large models can be transferred to smaller ones through instruction tuning. However, ToolLLM’s training is optimized for a broad variety of APIs without specialization. It remains uncertain whether the system can scale or adapt to a more structured, domain-specific API landscape, such as the one targeted by **Agora**.

Confucius [24] presents another approach to tool learning, this time emphasizing more complex tools — such as Google Maps — in tasks involving navigation between specified waypoints. Its central goal is to generalize effectively to unseen tools. The authors propose a multi-stage learning method, using a synthetic dataset built through iterative self-instruction. ChatGPT was employed to both generate diverse user queries and produce corresponding answers. Compared to prior work, including Toolformer [8], Confucius shows stronger performance in accessing and reasoning with previously unseen toolsets, achieving results comparable to large proprietary models like ChatGPT. Confucius trains a 7B-parameter model, reinforcing the viability of smaller, open models for tool use. However, similar to other general-purpose frameworks, it prioritizes breadth over specialization — a design choice that limits its applicability to narrowly defined, domain-specific scenarios like those targeted by **Agora**.

Gorilla [25] is a project aimed at building language models capable of handling a wide range of APIs. To support this goal, the authors created a dataset of 925 APIs with complex and overlapping functionality, sourced from platforms like TorchHub, TensorHub, and HuggingFace. For each API, they generated 10 instruction-style prompts, resulting in a large, curated dataset. Using this, they fine-tuned Gorilla, a LLaMA-2-7B model, which outperformed GPT-4 in executing API calls and significantly reduced hallucinations. Gorilla’s focus lies in generalizing API usage from examples, emphasizing scalability rather than managing interdependencies between APIs. While impressive, Gorilla

is primarily oriented toward APIs used in program synthesis — a domain that falls outside the scope of our work.

GPT4Tools [26] is a method for teaching language models to use external tools, with a particular focus on visual tasks. It leverages self-instruct, where the model generates its own training data for fine-tuning, enabling open-source models to perform complex visual reasoning without relying on proprietary systems. GPT4Tools distinguishes itself by emphasizing multi-modal tool use, especially those based on vision. Its dataset serves as a plug-and-play solution, allowing arbitrary language models to learn tool usage. Unlike approaches tailored to specific APIs, GPT4Tools prioritizes broad generalization across diverse and independent interfaces.

ToolAlpaca [28] is a multi-agent simulation framework designed to generate a diverse corpus of tool usage. In this sense, ToolAlpaca can be viewed as a generalization of **Agora** as it has been employed in the creation of a compression model. The resulting dataset contains 3988 tool-use instances from more than 400 real-world tool APIs spanning 50 distinct categories. Subsequently, the constructed corpus was employed to fine-tune compact language models, resulting in two models: ToolAlpaca-7B and ToolAlpaca-13B. Experimental results demonstrate that ToolAlpaca achieves effective generalized tool-use capabilities comparable to those of extremely large language models such as GPT-3.5, demonstrating that learning generalized tool-use ability is feasible for compact language models.

CREATOR [29] is a framework designed to enhance the ability of LLMs to generate and use their own tools for problem-solving. Unlike traditional methods where LLMs rely on pre-existing APIs or tools, CREATOR enables models to create new tools, by careful examination of user input. In short, for a given user query, CREATOR generates a Python code that can perform mathematical reasoning as well as invoke third-party APIs. Next, the LLM decides how to call a particular code (i.e. what parameters to use) and proceeds with the code execution. In cases where the generated code fails to compile, the tool generation process is resumed and the LLM is prompted to rectify the error. The authors of [29] evaluated CREATOR on a benchmark for mathematical reasoning, where it performed on par with state-of-the-art methods such as ChatGPT. As reported in [29], CREATOR

was not evaluated with third-party APIs, nor did it have the ability to learn to perform API-calls without examples.

In [30], the authors introduced LATM (LLMs As Tool Makers), a framework that supports the creation of new tools. Unlike CREATOR or previous work, LATM is focused on tool reuse and LLM specialization: one model is used to generate the required tool (GPT-4 in the experiments from [30]), and the other is used for tool usage (GPT-3.4). The authors compared their system with GPT-4 and discovered that their performance was similar to the latter; however the inference costs were much smaller, because of the division of labor between models as well as the caching of the generated tools. The specific reasoning tasks used in the evaluation were from the Big Bench dataset [32].

The paper [31] introduces a novel method for integrating large language models (LLMs) with external tools in a more efficient manner. Instead of costly finetuning or relying solely on in-context learning, the authors propose a system called ToolkenGPT, where tools are represented as special tokens that are part of the word embeddings, which can be generated by the model. These embeddings are integrated into the architecture of LLMs, allowing the models to effectively predict and utilize tools such as regular tokens during text generation. This approach improves performance in complex tasks, including numerical reasoning, knowledge-based question answering, and embodied decision making, without the need for extensive model retraining.

1) SUMMARY

As shown in Figure 3, existing methods vary widely in both the scale of the models they use and their flexibility in integrating new APIs. Notably, none of the approaches we reviewed support API-call chaining—a core feature of our work. Most efforts aim to expand API coverage, prioritizing general-purpose language models across broad task domains. However, they pay little attention to domain-specific expertise or to enhancing language models for specialized applications. Additionally, many of the tools they rely on lack support for data retrieval, a capability essential to our task. Domain specialization remains an underexplored area in tool-augmented language model research. For more approaches related to augmenting language models we defer the interested reader to [33].

C. MULTI-MODEL SYSTEMS

In [34], the authors introduced a complex concept of Intelligent Generative Agents (IGA), which is essentially a multi-agent System, where each agent has a certain LLM attached to it, as well as a universe of states, roles and various differing abilities. The concept of the LLM *plugin* is also introduced, which endows LLMs with the ability to engage third-party data. The contribution of [34] is on the conceptual side, leaving many details regarding IGA instantiation for further work.

The authors of [35] introduce a framework that allows the use of multiple models for text generation. As in our case, there is a distinction between the *base model*, which is partially similar to our *Interviewer* and the *assistant models*, which are similar to our experts. The system uses a latent variable framework to achieve this goal. In short, whenever generating a sequence of tokens t_1, \dots, t_n , for each t_i in the sequence, the base model decides whether t_i is generated by itself, or by one of the assistant models. This token-level discrete decision is learned via unsupervised learning. The work of [35] uses a similar approach to our parallel generation process, with a few contrasting features related to implementation and objectives, which we enumerate here: (i) the overall objective of [35] is to enhance the performance of a generative system, by combining two models instead of fine-tuning a single one; (ii) the setup explored in the work uses a single base and assistant model and is not preoccupied with external API calls (although the work could be extended in this direction); (iii) in our view, the system presented in [35] is less flexible, because the base model does not have the ability to moderate content from assistant models, but only to switch between them.

In [36] a framework called Expert-Token-Routing (ETR) was proposed to integrate multiple specialized large language models (LLMs) into a unified generalist system. The central idea is to represent expert models as tokens in the vocabulary of a meta-model, which routes queries to the most relevant expert based on their domain-specific expertise. This approach allows seamless interaction with multiple expert models while abstracting the complexity of routing from the user. This principle is very similar to that of **Agora**. Similar to our approach to construct expert LLMs, the authors fine-tuned domain-specific models using a synthetic dataset built from GPT-4 responses. They created the MMLU-Expert dataset, which includes questions from specialized domains such as astronomy and electrical engineering. The framework dynamically assigns queries to the most suitable expert, thus enhancing accuracy while avoiding the limitations of prompt-based methods, which typically lack depth in domain knowledge.

The evaluation demonstrates that ETR excels in selecting the right expert for each query, surpassing traditional methods such as prompt-based expert systems and router-based approaches. The framework proved effective in domains where specialized knowledge is critical, offering a scalable solution for generalist LLMs to leverage multiple experts dynamically. The authors showed that this synergistic approach improves performance in tasks requiring deep, specialized understanding across diverse fields.

D. KNOWLEDGE DISTILLATION AND SELF REFINEMENT

Knowledge distillation is a technique used to transfer the advanced capabilities of larger, more general language models to smaller, more efficient models. It is commonly applied to distill knowledge from proprietary models into

open-source alternatives. This approach contrasts with the trend set by OpenAI, which prioritizes the building of increasingly large, powerful, and general models. Instead, knowledge distillation focuses on creating smaller task-specific models, that can be achieved easily using this method.

In our work, we applied an ad-hoc knowledge distillation process to compress the more complex **Agora** system into a smaller, 7-billion-parameter model, as described in Section IV-C. Unlike the sophisticated techniques discussed in [37], we leveraged the proprietary GPT-4 model to generate complex, dependency-rich queries. We then used **Agora** to generate accurate responses. The resulting dataset was then used to fine-tune the smaller 7B model.

In [10] state-of-the-art language models such as GPT-3.5 and GPT-4.0, enhanced by Self-Refinement and RAG techniques are deployed to the task of taking an agricultural exam, with performance results surpassing that of humans (over 80% correctly answered questions), when both techniques (SR and RAG) are deployed.

Self-Refinement, first introduced in [38] is an approach used to improve the quality of a model's generated content by enforcing a feedback loop on the generated answer. Similar to human-like copy-editing, self refinement takes a generated text from model M , and uses the same model M to analyze the quality of the generated text. The feedback is extracted via a prompt that directs the model to make observations that are specific and actionable, that is, contain a concrete action that would improve the text. Next, M uses its feedback to improve its response. The feedback and refinement stages are repeated for a fixed number of steps or until the desired termination condition is reached. [38] reported performance improvements in seven text generation tasks, across three OpenAI language models: GPT-3.5, ChatGPT and GPT 4. Most notably, Self-Refinement achieves its best performance improvements in Dialogue Response over all evaluated models. Self-refinement is a technique that we are currently considering for future iterations of **Agora**.

VI. LIMITATIONS

In our experiments, the system performance remained below 80%, due to the sub-optimal performance of the experts. This shows that the system depends heavily on the quality of the experts, as even one poorly performing expert—if frequently utilized can have a significant impact on the overall performance of the system.

Our two evaluation scenarios: **Agora** (interviewer with k experts) and the compression model illustrate the necessary tradeoff between system scalability (a multi-model system with independent experts) versus resource utilization (the amount of memory/GPUs required to run such a multi-model system). We argue that **Agora** and its respective compression model can be used jointly. Whenever the overall system needs to scale to new domains, we can (i) create new expert models supporting the required knowledge and/or API support. (ii) use **Agora** to generate a new dataset reflecting

inter-domain dependencies, and (iii) create a compression model to be deployed as a stable final system. We have identified several other approaches to break the previously-mentioned tradeoff, which we propose in future work.

Guard-rails. Language models are known to hallucinate when responding to questions outside their area of expertise, and our models are no exception. Fortunately, tools such as Guardrails [39] offer practical solutions by preventing models from answering queries beyond their trained scope. While integrating guardrails is relatively straightforward, we have chosen to defer their deployment until the user-testing phase. At that stage, additional technical adjustments—beyond the scope of our research, methodology, and performance evaluation—will be implemented.

Language. The base models used in this work are trained primarily in English. Deploying our system as an app in Romania—or in other regions where English proficiency is limited—naturally presents a barrier to adoption. However, this is largely an implementation issue rather than a research one. Several practical solutions are available. Fine-tuning on alternative base models that support other languages, including Romanian, is straightforward. In fact, a Romanian-language base model already exists, and we are considering it for future work. Since our fine-tuning focuses on API learning and call context—not language-specific understanding—adapting the system to other languages is entirely feasible. Multilingual translation models also offer a reliable path to localization.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Agora and its compression models were developed as part of the FUTURAL project [6], with a clear objective: to provide a human-readable, AI-driven interface for accessing smart services in rural development. Many of these services generate complex, machine-readable data, making accessibility a challenge for non-experts. **Agora** bridges this gap by translating raw data into clear, human-readable insights.

Over the next three years, as part of FUTURAL, **Agora** will be expanded to support a vast ecosystem of over 47 APIs, covering diverse domains such as drought and flood assessment, biodiversity analysis, and rural service accessibility. Scaling to such a broad set of heterogeneous APIs is a challenge for which **Agora**'s architecture was specifically designed. Our ongoing research and implementation will test this claim.

Enhancing the Interviewer. To improve **Agora**'s Interviewer model, we are moving beyond reliance on system prompts. Instead, we plan to fine-tune our model on previously unseen APIs while incorporating chain-of-thought reasoning. This upgrade will enable the Interviewer to break down complex tasks into smaller, manageable steps, significantly improving the quality and accuracy of responses.

However, a key challenge remains: creating the right fine-tuning dataset for this task. Identifying or generating a dataset that effectively teaches the model to reason step-by-step is a

non-trivial research problem that we are actively working to solve.

Optimizing Performance: Smarter Expert Activation.

Running all experts simultaneously is computationally expensive and inefficient. To address this, we are exploring two key optimization strategies:

- Expert Merging – Combining similar experts to reduce redundancy.
- Selective Activation – Introducing a control layer where the Interviewer generates control tokens. Instead of engaging all experts at once, lightweight binary classification models (acting as “yes/no” switches) evaluate whether expert intervention is needed.

This approach significantly reduces memory usage, as these classification models require far less computational power than running multiple experts in parallel. By implementing this, we only need:

- A single base model for all experts (assuming a shared architecture);
- LoRA adapters loaded into memory;
- Lightweight “yes/no” classifiers managing control flow.

Once an expert is activated, it executes independently, ensuring no redundant models run in parallel. This method balances efficiency and precision, making **Agora** scalable for real-world deployment.

FIGURE 13. Prototype Agora interface.

Real-World Deployment & User Feedback. Beyond technical scalability, **Agora** is being prepared for widespread deployment. Figure 13 illustrates our prototype interface, which has been used in our early development phase. Once deployed at scale, we will be able to analyze real-world user interactions and measure user satisfaction, ensuring that **Agora** not only functions effectively but also delivers a seamless experience for end users.

With this roadmap, we aim to make **Agora** a cornerstone of AI-driven rural development, combining cutting-edge AI techniques with practical, real-world usability.

Deployment in other expert domains The **Agora** methodology for building domain-expert language models can be applied to other fields—provided two key conditions are met:

- The expertise is data-driven.
- The data is interpretable by human experts, without requiring complex modeling.

For instance, **Agora** is not suited for generating weather forecasts directly from raw sensor grid data, which requires specialized numerical models.

Agora is especially effective in domains where information must be drawn from multiple data sources with interdependencies, as explored in this work. It may be less effective when questions are broad or not tightly focused on data interpretation. That said, future developments—such as more advanced dataset generation techniques and stronger 8B-scale models—are likely to expand **Agora**’s capabilities as the field of LLMs continues to evolve.

**APPENDIX A
API-CALL SYNTAX**

The syntax of calling the **Current Date** API is found in Figure 14, for the **Crops** API Figure 16, for the **Weather & climate** API in Figure 15, and for the **Aggregation** API - in Figure 17.

```
<TODAY> -> Monday, 29 July 2024, 10:42 AM </TODAY>
```

FIGURE 14. An example of the *Current date* call & response.

```
<METEO> [(Iasi, Romania, "04-08-2024 00:00 - 04-08-2024 23:59")] ->
Weather in Iasi, country Romania, admin Iasi, on 03-08-2024:
{
  'time': (3, ... 21),
  'temperature: (C)': (21, ... 27),
  'wind_speed (km/h)': ('8-17', ... '8-16'),
  'wind_direction': ('WNW', ... 'ENE'),
  'precipitation_size (mm/3h)': (' - ', ... ' - '),
  'precipitation_probability': ('0%', ... '5%'),
  'cloud_cover': ('Mostly cloudy', ... 'Clear with few low clouds'),
  'uv_index': '7'
}. </METEO>
```

FIGURE 15. An example of the *Weather & climate* call & response.

```
<SEEDS> tomato ->
{
  "Common name": "Tomato",
  "Scientific name": "Solanum lycopersicum",
  "Sowing month": "March",
  "Ideal sowing temperature": "15-25C",
  "Precipitation conditions \\/ annually": "500-700 mm"
} </SEEDS>
```

FIGURE 16. An example of the *Current date* call & response.

```
<COMPUTE> min(1, 2, 3, 4, 5) -> 1 </COMPUTE>
```

FIGURE 17. An example of the *Current date* call & response.

**APPENDIX B
PROMPTS FOR BUILDING AGORA**

A. PROMPTS FOR BUILDING TRAINING DATASETS FOR EXPERTS

Below, we present the prompts used to generate datasets for each API, along with sample outputs from the generated data for clarity.

Crops and Aggregation: The question-answer pairs in the datasets for the crops and aggregation APIs were generated directly using GPT-4, without any additional filtering, by employing the prompts shown in Figures 18, 19 and 20. Each API is linked to a corresponding back-end function, which either returns the current date or queries an internal database for sowing conditions.

For handling the current date and weather & climate APIs, we generated the question and the parameters for the calls using GPT-4o. We began by taking a list of Romanian cities along with their latitude and longitude, which were later needed when interacting with the weather and climate API.

```
Pick an edible species S. Formulate a question which asks
if species S can be successfully cultivated in
certain conditions or what are the ideal conditions
for it.

Formulate an answer that uses an API call to a database,
as in the following example. The answer must always
contain some text that is not part of the API call
and must repeat the information from the API call
that is relevant to the question.

Example output:
"The ideal sowing temperature for apples is <SEEDS> apple
-> {'Common name':'Apple','Scientific name':'Malus
domestica','Sowing month':'March','Ideal sowing
temperature':'4-15 C','Precipitation conditions /
annually':'50-100 mm'} </SEEDS> between 4-15 degrees
Celsius."

Ask about temperature, precipitation or month of sowing,
and include the answer in the same format as the
example, but change the text that is not part of the
API call. Make the text sound naturally even when the
API call is not present.

Repeat the above process for a number of 10 questions
with different S.

The answer should only contain the 10 questions and
answers, in csv format - each pair on a new line, the
question and the answer separated by "," and
enclosed in quotes.

Be creative in rephrasing each question so that they seem
different.
```

FIGURE 18. Prompt for generating dataset for Crops expert dataset.

```
Generate 50 examples:
- one paragraph including AT LEAST 10 different float/
integer numbers. The numbers must appear in a
creative way inside a context or as a JSON. This
paragraph must contain one or more questions about
average or minimim or maximum value of these numbers.
- the answer to the questions annotated with a call to a
function avg or min or max
Only give the output, with no additinal text. Be creative
.
```

FIGURE 19. Prompt for generating dataset for Aggregation expert dataset.

We wrote by hand 190 different time expressions that we considered plausible to be used in a query. Our API provides, by design, hourly data for intervals of up to three days, daily data for intervals of up to two months, and monthly data for longer time spans. If the user’s query includes the name of a country, it is passed as a parameter in the call. If no country is specified, the parameter value defaults to “???”, in which case the system assumes the query refers to the largest city with the given name. In this situation, the country name is retrieved automatically from a database. We filtered out examples where data retrieval from our sources was unsuccessful and then tasked GPT-4o-mini with adjusting the current date and all related dates in each example. This ensured that the final dataset does not contain examples tied exclusively to the original creation date. In addition to fully annotated examples, we realized the need for more examples focusing solely on the weather & climate API call parameters. To boost the model’s ability to select the correct parameters for this API, we generated additional examples that contained only the question and the call parameters, omitting the final result and text reasoning about the retrieved data.

```
You are given a list of cities paired with associated
temporal expressions:
1. city: ..., country: ..., time expression: ...
2. city: ..., country: ..., time expression: ...
...
Generate 10 different weather-related queries that
include all the given pairs of
cities and their associated temporal expressions in a
single paragraph.
Each query must take each city with its associated
temporal expression and include
it, without mixing them.
The queries must be varied and distinct, but make logical
sense.
A third of the queries must include the country names,
another third must not
include the country names, and the last third must
include the country names only
for some cities.
The country name, if included, doesn't have to be
separated by comma from the city
name, it can be included in the context naturally.
Make sure the verb tenses are correct in relation to the
temporal expressions.
Assume that the reference date is the current date when
the queries are being asked,
making the temporal expressions relative to this date.
Following generated query, also provide a list specifying
for each city:
- the city name
- the country (if included) or "???" if not included in
the query
- the time interval that the query refers to in the
format
"DD-MM-YYYY HH:MM - DD-MM-YYYY HH:MM".
``` [(city, country, time interval)] ```
Format each result on a new line with the following tags:
``` <start> generated text without quotes <end> [(city,
country, time interval)] ```
Do not include other text aside from the generated
queries.
```

FIGURE 20. Prompt for generating dataset for Weather & climate expert dataset.

Table 4 outlines the number of examples generated for training each expert.

TABLE 4. The number of examples used to train each expert model.

Expert name	Number of examples
Weather & climate	514 (present & future queries) 1690 (past queries) 7139 (without results)
Crops	2128
Aggregation	2461

B. PROMPTS FOR CROSS-DOMAIN QUESTIONS

To generate questions that require API calls from both the Weather & Climate and Aggregation experts, we used the prompt shown in Figure 21. We used similar prompts for all other cross-domain questions.

Generate K questions about the weather in Romania, requesting the average, minimum or maximum values of certain weather parameters.

Be creative and use different cities and temporal expressions in your questions. Use any year from 2000 until 2024.

Generate questions that ask about temperature, is it hot/cold, precipitations, will it rain/snow, wind, UV index, natural disasters, humidity, atmospheric pressure etc.

Always include words like "minimum", "maximum", "average", "max", "min", "highest", "lowest" etc. in your questions.

FIGURE 21. Prompt for generating dataset for Aggregation expert dataset.

Table 5 shows the number of examples generated for each combination of API calls that we deemed necessary and that involve at least two experts.

TABLE 5. The number of examples with combinations of API calls.

Combination of experts	Number of examples after filtering
Weather & climate + Crops	2748
Weather & climate + Aggregation	275

C. FINE-TUNING HYPER-PARAMETERS

We applied the same training settings consistently across all our fine-tuning experiments.

A constant learning rate (LR) was suboptimal, so we adopted a cosine LR scheduler with a maximum value of $1e-4$, which provided better convergence. Due to restricted memory, we used a batch size of 1 and trained the model for 2 epochs with a maximum input sequence length of 2048 tokens. We applied gradient clipping at 0.3 and set the weight decay to 0.1 to stabilize the training process.

For the LoRA hyperparameters, we have set both alpha and rank (r) to 32.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

REFERENCES

- [1] InvestRomania. (2022). *Internet Infrastructure*. Accessed: Jul. 22, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://investromania.gov.ro/web/internet-infrastructure/>
- [2] Business Agency Association (BAA), "Jointly preparing the conditions in the agricultural and connected sectors in the BSB area for the digital transformation (BSB smart farming)," Dunarea de Jos, Univ. Galati, Galati, Romania, Tech. Rep., 2021. Accessed: Dec. 12, 2024.
- [3] S. Rezayi, Z. Liu, Z. Wu, C. Dhakal, B. Ge, C. Zhen, T. Liu, and S. Li, "AgriBERT: Knowledge-infused agricultural language models for matching food and nutrition," in *Proc. 31st Int. Joint Conf. Artif. Intell.*, Jul. 2022, pp. 5150–5156, doi: [10.24963/ijcai.2022/715](https://doi.org/10.24963/ijcai.2022/715).
- [4] N. Koldunov and T. Jung, "Local climate services for all, courtesy of large language models," *Commun. Earth Environ.*, vol. 5, no. 1, p. 13, Jan. 2024, doi: [10.1038/s43247-023-01199-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-01199-1).
- [5] T. T. Nguyen, J. Brandstetter, A. Kapoor, J. K. Gupta, and A. Grover, "ClimaX: A foundation model for weather and climate," in *Proc. 40th Int. Conf. Mach. Learn.*, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–14.
- [6] Futural Project. (2024). *Futural Project—agriculture and Climate*. Accessed: Sep. 14, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://futural-project.eu/>
- [7] A. Vaswani, N. Shazeer, N. Parmar, J. Uszkoreit, L. Jones, A. N. Gomez, Ł. Kaiser, and I. Polosukhin, "Attention is all you need," *Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 30, pp. 5998–6008, Jun. 2017.
- [8] T. Schick, J. Dwivedi-Yu, R. Dessì, R. Raileanu, M. Lomeli, L. Zettlemoyer, N. Cancedda, and T. Scialom, "Toolformer: Language models can teach themselves to use tools," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 36, Jan. 2024, pp. 1–16.
- [9] (2024). *KissanAI*. Accessed: Jul. 22, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://kissan.ai/>
- [10] B. Silva, L. Nunes, R. Estevão, V. Aski, and R. Chandra, "GPT-4 as an agronomist assistant? Answering agriculture exams using large language models," 2023, *arXiv:2310.06225*.
- [11] H. Touvron, T. Lavril, G. Izacard, X. Martinet, M.-A. Lachaux, T. Lacroix, B. Rozière, N. Goyal, E. Hambro, F. Azhar, A. Rodriguez, A. Joulin, E. Grave, and G. Lample, "LLaMA: Open and efficient foundation language models," 2023, *arXiv:2302.13971*.
- [12] P. Lewis, E. Perez, A. Piktus, F. Petroni, V. Karpukhin, N. Goyal, H. Küttler, M. Lewis, W.-t. Yih, T. Rocktäschel, S. Riedel, and D. Kiela, "Retrieval-augmented generation for knowledge-intensive NLP tasks," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, Jan. 2020, pp. 9459–9474.
- [13] S. Robertson and H. Zaragoza, "The probabilistic relevance framework: BM25 and beyond," *Found. Trends Inf. Retr.*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 333–389, 2009.
- [14] B. Wang and A. Komatsuzaki. (2021). *Gpt-j-6b: A 6 Billion Parameter Autoregressive Language Model*. Accessed: Aug. 12, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/kingoflolz/mesh-transformer-jax>
- [15] A. Alford. (2024). *Meta Releases Llama 3 Open-Source LLM*. Accessed: May. 7, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.infoq.vcom/news/2024/05/meta-llama-3/>
- [16] J. E. Hu, Y. Shen, P. Wallis, Z. Allen-Zhu, Y. Li, S. Wang, and W. Chen, "LoRA: Low-rank adaptation of large language models," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Learn. Represent.*, Jan. 2021, pp. 1–16.
- [17] T. Dettmers, A. Pagnoni, A. Holtzman, and L. Zettlemoyer, "QLoRA: Efficient finetuning of quantized LLMs," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, Jan. 2023, pp. 10088–10115.
- [18] (2024). *Agri1*. Accessed: Sep. 4, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.agri1.ai/en/>
- [19] S. Chen, G. Long, J. Jiang, D. Liu, and C. Zhang, "Foundation models for weather and climate data understanding: A comprehensive survey," 2023, *arXiv:2312.03014*.
- [20] J. Devlin, M. Chang, K. Lee, and K. Toutanova, "BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding," in *Proc. NaacL-HLT*, Minneapolis, MN, USA, Jan. 2019, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 4171–4186.

- [21] Y. Gao, Y. Xiong, X. Gao, K. Jia, J. Pan, Y. Bi, Y. Dai, J. Sun, M. Wang, and H. Wang, "Retrieval-augmented generation for large language models: A survey," 2023, *arXiv:2312.10997*.
- [22] L. Yuan, Y. Chen, X. Wang, Y. Fung, H. Peng, and H. Ji, "CRAFT: Customizing LLMs by creating and retrieving from specialized toolsets," in *Proc. 12th Int. Conf. Learn. Represent.*, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–16.
- [23] Y. Qin, S. Liang, Y. Ye, K. Zhu, L. Yan, Y. Lu, Y. Lin, X. Cong, X. Tang, B. Qian, S. Zhao, R. Tian, R. Xie, J. Zhou, M. Gerstein, D. Li, Z. Liu, and M. Sun, "ToolLLM: Facilitating large language models to master 16000+ real-world Apis," in *Proc. 12th Int. Conf. Learn. Represent.*, Jan. 2024, pp. 1–19. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=dHng200Jjr>
- [24] S. Gao, Z. Shi, M. Zhu, B. Fang, X. Xin, P. Ren, Z. Chen, J. Ma, and Z. Ren, "Confucius: Iterative tool learning from introspection feedback by easy-to-difficult curriculum," in *Proc. AAAI Conf. Artif. Intell.*, Mar. 2024, vol. 38, no. 16, pp. 18030–18038.
- [25] S. G. Patil, T. Zhang, X. Wang, and J. E. Gonzalez, "Gorilla: Large language model connected with massive Apis," 2023, *arXiv:2305.15334*.
- [26] R. Yang, S. Lin, Y. Li, S. Zhao, Y. Ge, X. Li, and Y. Shan, "GPT4Tools: Teaching large language model to use tools via self-instruction," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 36, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–17.
- [27] W.-L. Chiang, Z. Li, Z. Lin, Y. Sheng, Z. Wu, H. Zhang, L. Zheng, S. Zhuang, Y. Zhuang, J. E. Gonzalez, I. Stoica, and E. P. Xing. (2023). *Vicuna: An Open-source Chatbot Impressing Gpt-4 With 90% Chatgpt Quality*. Accessed: Sep. 12, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://lmsys.org/blog/2023-03-30-vicuna/>
- [28] Q. Tang, Z. Deng, H. Lin, X. Han, Q. Liang, B. Cao, and L. Sun, "ToolAlpaca: Generalized tool learning for language models with 3000 simulated cases," 2023, *arXiv:2306.05301*.
- [29] C. Qian, C. Han, Y. R. Fung, Y. Qin, Z. Liu, and H. Ji, "CREATOR: Tool creation for disentangling abstract and concrete reasoning of large language models," 2023, *arXiv:2305.14318*.
- [30] T. Cai, X. Wang, T. Ma, X. Chen, and D. Zhou, "Large language models as tool makers," in *Proc. 12th Int. Conf. Learn. Represent.*, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–14.
- [31] S. Hao, T. Liu, Z. Wang, and Z. Hu, "ToolkenGPT: Augmenting frozen language models with massive tools via tool embeddings," in *Proc. 37th Conf. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, 2023, pp. 1–13. [Online]. Available: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=BHXsb69bSx>
- [32] A. Srivastava et al., "Beyond the imitation game: Quantifying and extrapolating the capabilities of language models," in *Proc. Trans. Mach. Learn. Res.*, Jan. 2022, pp. 1–95.
- [33] G. Mialon, R. Dessì, M. Lomelí, C. Nalmpantis, R. Pasunuru, R. Raileanu, B. Rozière, T. Schick, J. Dwivedi-Yu, A. Çelikilimaz, É. Grave, Y. LeCun, and T. Scialom, "Augmented language models: A survey," *Trans. Mach. Learn. Res.*, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–33.
- [34] Y. Talebirad and A. Nadiri, "Multi-agent collaboration: Harnessing the power of intelligent LLM agents," 2023, *arXiv:2306.03314*.
- [35] S. Zejiang Shen, H. Lang, B. Wang, Y. Kim, and D. Sontag, "Learning to decode collaboratively with multiple language models," 2024, *arXiv:2403.03870*.
- [36] Z. Chai, G. Wang, J. Su, T. Zhang, X. Huang, X. Wang, J. Xu, J. Yuan, H. Yang, F. Wu, and Y. Yang, "An expert is worth one token: Synergizing multiple expert LLMs as generalist via expert token routing," 2024, *arXiv:2403.16854*.
- [37] X. Xu, M. Li, C. Tao, T. Shen, R. Cheng, J. Li, C. Xu, D. Tao, and T. Zhou, "A survey on knowledge distillation of large language models," 2024, *arXiv:2402.13116*.
- [38] A. Madaan, N. Tandon, P. Gupta, S. Hallinan, L. Gao, S. Wiegrefe, U. Alon, N. Dziri, S. Prabhume, Y. Yang, S. Welleck, B. P. Majumder, S. Gupta, A. Yazdanbakhsh, and P. Clark, "Self-refine: Iterative refinement with self-feedback," in *Proc. Adv. Neural Inf. Process. Syst.*, vol. 36, Jan. 2023, pp. 1–24.
- [39] X. Dong, R. Mu, G. Jin, Y. Qi, J. Hu, X. Zhao, J. Meng, W. Ruan, and X. Huang, "Building guardrails for large language models," 2024, *arXiv:2402.01822*.

ALEXANDRA UDRESCU received the engineering degree in computer science from the Faculty of Automatic Control and Computers, National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest, where she is currently pursuing the master's degree. She is a Computer Scientist specializing in algorithms, formal methods, and machine learning.

DAN-MATEI POPOVICI received the Ph.D. degree from the National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest, in 2012. He was a Research Fellow with the Clausthal University of Technology and ICUB (University of Bucharest's Research Institute). He is currently an Associate Professor with the Computer Science Department, National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest. His research interests include formal verification techniques for computer networks, computing research education, and NLP using language models.

• • •